

Rare Earth Complexes of Some Amino Acids : A Potentiometric Study

SANTOSH D. MAKHIJANI and SATENDRA P. SANGAL*

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University, Nagpur

Manuscript received 9 September 1976, accepted 18 March 1977

Stability constants of 1 : 1 complexes of Sc(III), Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) with Glycine, Asparagine and Glutamine at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.2 M NaClO₄ have been determined by Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique. Free energies of the above said complexes are also reported. The trend of stability constants irrespective of amino acids under investigation is found to be Sc(III) > Y(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III). In terms of amino acids, the stability constants of any particular rare earth ion decreased in order Glycine > Glutamine > Asparagine.

EXTENSIVE work has been reported on metal chelates of amino acids with various metal ions. But, so as to obtain the trend and values of stability constants of the complexes of rare earths with amino acids in terms of metal ions as well as amino acids, it was proposed to study the complexes of some rare earths with various amino acids containing different substituent groups. The metal ions selected for study are Sc(III), Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), and Nd(III) and amino acids are Glycine, Asparagine and Glutamine. The studies include the determination of "Practical" proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.2 M NaClO₄. The stability constants are obtained by the method of Bjerum-Calvin pH-titration technique^{1,2} as used by Irving and Rossotti³. The free energy changes accompanying the equilibrium are also reported.

Experimental

Chemicals: Stock solutions of 0.01 M Glycine (E. Merk, Germany), Glutamine (BDH, made in England) and Asparagine (Reanal, Hungary) were prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water. The metal solutions were prepared by converting oxides into perchlorates in usual manner. These solutions were standardized by EDTA method⁴. Perchloric acid (0.1 M, A. R. Merck), sodium hydroxide (approx. 1 M), potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 M, BDH) and sodium perchlorate (1 M) (all analytical reagents) were prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water. Sodium hydroxide was standardized with potassium hydrogen phthalate. potentiometrically.

Apparatus: A pH-meter with a combined glass calomel electrode was used for pH-measurements. The nitrogen gas was passed continuously during the course of titration. The cell was immersed in an electronically operated thermostat having an accuracy of ± 0.1° and also, the contents of the cell were stirred continuously during the titrations.

Results and Discussion

Proton-Ligand and Metal-Ligand Stability Constants: In all the cases, at the initial stages of the titration the ligand titration curve was above the acid titration curve due to the basic properties of the amino group present in amino acids, which can easily accept a proton from the strongly acidic medium. In general, reactions occurring during the dissociation of the protonated amino acid molecule can be shown as :

The "Practical" proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were obtained by usual equations as in previous communications^{5,6}. The values of proton ligand and metal ligand (1 : 1) stability constants so obtained by using half \bar{n} -values methods are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 30°, AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.2M NaClO₄.

Metal	Constant	Glycine	Amino Acid Glutamine	Asparagine
H ⁺	log K ^H	9.225	8.815	8.555
	log K ^H	2.250	2.210	2.085
	log β ^H	11.475	11.025	10.640
Sc(III)	log K ₁	7.749	7.405	7.083
Y(III)	log K ₁	5.055	4.720	4.425
La(III)	log K ₁	3.850	3.710	3.525
Ce(III)	log K ₁	4.435	3.945	3.775
Pr(III)	log K ₁	4.500	4.275	4.085
Nd(III)	log K ₁	4.615	4.530	4.260

* Senior Author

Precipitation was observed in all the cases, and hence calculations were done only in pH-range where there was no precipitation. The precipitation may be due to the hydroxo complex formation, which can be explained in the following manner :

(where AA = amino acid)

Free Energies : The Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁷ has been used to obtain the free energy changes (ΔG) of the reactions. The total free energy change is given by equation

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta \quad (3)$$

where β is the overall stability constant. The values of free energies so obtained are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGIES OF THE COMPLEXES OF RARE EARTH IONS WITH AMINO ACIDS AT 30°C ($\mu = 0.2 M$ NaClO₄).

Metal	Glycine	Glutamine	Asparagine
H ⁺	-16.015	-15.386	-14.849
Sc(III)	-10.815	-10.334	-9.885
Y(III)	-7.055	-6.587	-6.176
La(III)	-5.373	-5.178	-4.920
Ce(III)	-6.217	-5.506	-5.268
Pr(III)	-6.280	-5.966	-5.701
Nd(III)	-6.441	-6.322	-5.945

From Table 1 it can be seen that the trend of stability constants for all the amino acids under investigation is same i.e. Sc(III) > Y(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III). Thus, the statement "stability increases with the decrease in ionic radii" is proved in the present case also. Table 1 also reveals that, proton-ligand as well as metal-ligand stability constants of the amino acids follow the same order Glycine > Glutamine > Asparagine.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. C. V. N. Rao,, Director Incharge, Laxminarayan Institute of Technology for providing necessary facilities and to Prof. N. Majumder, Director, National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nagpur for granting permission to one of them (SDM) for working at L. I. T.

References

1. J. BJERRUM "Metal Ammine formation in aqueous solution" (Haase : Copenhagen) 1941, 133.
2. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
3. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
4. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical uses of ethylenediamine-tetraacetic acid" (D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc.) 1957, pp. 174, 181.
5. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 788.
6. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 448.
7. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASI'LEV, "Instability constants of complex compounds", (D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New Jersey), 1960, p. 74.